

DEVELOPMENT OF MARKETING COMMUNICATIONS IN CONSULTING SERVICES

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Abstract. Consulting services, modern business system, in the places of sale of products professional assistance to consultants and service personnel indicating that consultants are primarily engaged in consulting and are held accountable for completion.

Keywords: Consulting, business, service, communication, client, advice, enterprise, problem.

РАЗВИТИЕ МАРКЕТИНГОВЫХ КОММУНИКАЦИЙ В КОНСАЛТИНГОВЫХ УСЛУГАХ

Аннотация. Консультационные услуги, современная бизнес-система, в местах реализации продукции профессиональная помощь консультантам и обслуживающему персоналу с указанием того, что консультанты в основном занимаются консультированием и несут ответственность за выполнение.

Ключевые слова: Консалтинг, бизнес, услуга, общение, клиент, консультация, предприятие, проблема.

The communication process in consulting services embodies many concepts and concepts, and the problems encountered in it are improving day by day. In contrast to marketing communication in consulting services, like the process of marketing communication, the consultant and the client face challenges such as the contradictions between the consultant and the client, the consultant's having to face various emotional influences, and even the client's resistance in identifying the problem.

A simplified concept of communication consulting services is nothing more than a shift in marketing - an active transfer of information to a consumer (client). At the same time, the promotion provides advice, consultation, opinions and comments, goods, prices, conditions of sale, i.e. marketing provides the necessary level of awareness of the benefits and advantages that the potential consumer (client) can receive through its elements.

Advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, and community relations are the main means of promotion in marketing communication. All of these tools are used to achieve corporate advertising and marketing goals. Consulting services marketing marketing communication is almost the same, but other tools are added to achieve its goals, we will consider these tools later.

The communication process can be described using a communicative model. He provides for the implementation of the activities under his command.

1. Finding the target audience and determining its description
2. to provide information about the company and the product to potential customers.
3. to determine the expected reaction
4. increasing the goodwill of the audience

5. Encourage the customer to buy

In addition to the above activities in the marketing of consulting services, there are a few more must be added. These are

6. to determine the causes of the problems encountered by the client

7. emotional preparation of the client

8. implementation of the teaching process

9. and others

In this model, there are several basic conditions that can greatly increase the effectiveness of information transmission. For example, the sender of information must know exactly what kind of audience he wants to interest and what kind of reaction he wants to get from it. Information odadvertising, consultant advice is provided. It should ensure that the final result achieves the goal in the sense of not only advertising, the transfer of consultant information, but also establish a feedback and, therefore, allow to evaluate the response reaction of the audience.

When solving any problem, different consultants may use different methods and methods based on their knowledge and opinion, but in the end, any consultant will explain the cause of the problem and his opinion about its solution.

Before starting work, each consultant provides detailed explanations about which direction and methods to use, and each consultant works in a direction that is convenient for him.

Different approaches can be used to solve the problem facing each company or individual. Each approach helps to clarify the issue. Usually, when a consultant comes to a new enterprise, the first part of his work is very difficult, he usually faces various forms of resistance.

Table 1

Hthe main models of counseling on the character of amkor

The role to play	Model type		
	An unequal union	The doctor is the patient	Full cooperation
Troubleshooter	Customer	Consultant	Client/Consultant
A provider of information and ideas	Customer	Consultant	Client/Consultant
Decision generator (producer)	Consultant	Consultant	Client/Consultant
Decision maker	Customer	Customer	Client/Consultant

When working with an enterprise or certain individuals, a consultant is allocated according to the level of problems.

First level. In it, the client mainly points out that he is not able to achieve his goals, the level of knowledge of his employees, and so on. All this will be related to the general activity of the enterprise. Almost all companies use such expressions.

Second level. Employees are more busy with other activities, meetings are attended by only two people, employees do not understand the principle of operation of the system. This brings the matter closer to clarification. This problem exists in almost all enterprises.

The third level. it took into account the level of approach of each employee to the issue.

When the consultant reaches all three levels, the questions asked should be clear and clever. For example

The first step is to determine what type of business or technical problem the consultant is facing.

At the second level. the causes of the problem in the enterprise and their ability to influence are determined.

At the third level, you are asked what is your share in the problem.

Now, if we turn our attention to the third level, the employee you are talking to uses expressions like I have nothing to do with the problem, I am not involved in the problem, this is a healthy point. Usually, when an employee knows about a problem, he answers like this, and when you ask the consultant what you would do if you knew about it, 95% of the employees will start to answer.

The consultant always works with two aspects: the first is with the factors that cause the problem of the enterprise, and the second is with the emotional qualities of the client. In this case, it helps in the formation of the relationship between the client and the consultant, and provides direct assistance in solving the problem. The effectiveness of client-consultant relations is based mainly on: trust, character, responsibility, personal needs. The effectiveness of the consultant mainly depends on the responsibility of the client and the integrity of the consultant. Each consultant has three main roles in the enterprise. As they put it:

Table 2

No	Consultant role	Customer	Problems
1	Expert	the client was able to clearly see the problem. He was able to choose the right specialist to solve the problem He imagined the outcome of the problem and thought about its solutions. The customer is fully responsible for the problem.	Recruiting other employees of the enterprise with technical measures difficulties in attracting a manager
2	Doctor	the consultant identifies the problem and clearly shows its solution accepts the suggestions of the consultant and follows them If the consultant responds correctly to the consultation, the client has responded to its implementation	the problem lies in the diagnosis, and the consultant is afraid to make a mistake the customer is responsible for the application of the solution Is the client ready to solve this problem himself after a similar problem?

3	Coach	asks for help if he does not know what caused the problem does not know what form of help to accept does not know which form of realization is most convenient As a result of mutual cooperation with the consultant, the client learns many aspects.	Even if the solution is obvious, it may be available if the client does not want to use it does not know how to help solve the problem the consultant may appear to be underqualified.
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From the above, it can be said that the relationship between the consultant and the client directly helps to solve the problem.

Consulting services are considered an integral part of the modern business system. When we talk about the types of consulting in the places where products are sold, it is necessary to talk about the duties of consultants in the product sales system.

- First, professional assistance to the sales staff of consultants shows. Experienced consultants assist new and existing clients in various situations and participate in best practices. Because of this, they quickly know the general situation and get familiar with the threat of the problem, and have sufficient knowledge and experience about ways to solve it;

- Secondly, consultants are mainly engaged in consulting. Consultants are responsible for the quality and completion of the consultation. Service personnel are responsible for the full implementation of the received advice;

- Thirdly, consulting is an independent service. Consultant wanted evaluates the situation and makes objective recommendations, in which his personal interests are not taken into account.

- Fourth - motivation. Every enterprise increases the interests of its employees to achieve the goal, whether it is an individual or a team. Consultants at the points of sale of their products advise their subordinates and help them choose a strategy.

- improving the psychological environment of the enterprise;
- enrichment of work content;
- production of a reward system;
- employee performance evaluation.

Based on the above, point-of-sale consultants deal with issues such as: advertising, corporate relations and public relations, customer after-sales service, design, marketing, market research, marketing strategy, new product development, pricing, retail and mediation, automation, equipment operation and maintenance, material processing, internal material distribution management, packaging, product design, quality control, stock management, raw material management, determining the number and duration of control, determining the type of control based on selection, employee knowledge level determination

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